

LOCATION, CLASSIFICATION AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF NEIGHBORHOODS IN KASHKADARYA REGION

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Abstract: *The neighborhood institute is of great importance in the life of Uzbekistan. The neighborhood serves as the most important link in the formation and development of historical traditions, national and universal values, customs, humanism and patriotism. Today, when the neighborhood institution is developing more and more in multinational Uzbekistan, the neighborhood has its own place and ethno-regional aspects based on the specific characteristics of each region, and such a factor is typical for the neighborhoods of Kashkadarya.*

Key words: *Neighborhood, value, traditions, nation, ethnos, village, citizen, district, village, city, tradition, family, region. people, center, enterprise, neighborhood.*

It is known that Kashkadarya region was established on November 1, 1924. From February 17, 1927 to January 15, 1938, it was under the status of Kashkadarya district. On January 15, 1938, it was annexed to Bukhara region. It was reorganized on January 20, 1943. January 25, 1960 joined the Surkhandarya region. It was re-established on February 7, 1964. The province is located in the south-west of the republic, in the Kashkadarya basin, on the western edge of the Pamir-Aloy mountain system, between the Amudarya and Zarafshan rivers, and the Hisar and Zarafshan mountain ranges. It borders Bukhara to the northwest, Surkhandarya to the southeast, Turkmenistan to the southwest and west, Tajikistan and Samarkand to the east. The area is 28.6 thousand km². It includes 13 rural districts (Dehkanabad, Kasbi, Kitab, Koson, Mirishkor,

Mubarak, Nishon, Chirakchi, Shahrisabz, Yakkabog‘, Qamashi, Karshi, Guzor), 12 cities (Beshkent, Kitab, Koson, Mubarak , Tallimarjon, Chiraqi, Shahrisabz, Yakkabog, New Nishan, Qamashi, Karshi, Guzor), there are 4 towns (Dehkhanaabad, Miroqi, Eski Yakkabog, Kashkadarya). The center is the city of Karshi. The average population density was 83.7 people per 1 km. The population of the city was 587,500 people.

As of 2021, 768 citizens’ assemblies were operating in the region. 250,800 people live in the city of Karshi, the regional center, and there are mainly Uzbeks (91%), as well

	Туманлар	Жами	Шаҳарда жойлашган	Туман марказида жойлашган	Туман марказигача 30 км бўлган масофада жойлашган	Туман марказидан 30 км ва ундан олисида жойлашган	Чегара (ёки анклав) ҳудудида жойлашган
Туманлар:		796	102	146	425	101	22
1.	Қарши ш	62	62	0	0	0	0
2.	Шаҳрисабз ш	40	40	0	0	0	0
3.	Ўзгўр т	51	0	10	34	6	1
4.	Дехқонобод т	48	0	23	12	10	3
5.	Қасби т	42	0	7	32	3	0
6.	Қитоб т	59	0	13	42	3	1
7.	Қосон т	70	0	22	43	5	0
8.	Қамашн т	60	0	10	46	4	0
9.	Қарши т	58	0	7	44	7	0
10.	Қирншқор т	40	0	9	21	7	3
11.	Қуборак т	25	0	8	10	7	0
12.	Нншон т	36	0	9	14	6	7
13.	Қнрокчи т	86	0	15	50	21	0
14.	Шаҳрнсабз т	57	0	3	37	10	7
15.	Яққабоғ т	62	0	10	40	12	0

as Tajiks, Turkmens, Russians, Kazakhs, Ukrainians, Azerbaijanis, Koreans, Kyrgyz, Turks, Belarusians and representatives of various nationalities. There are 046 settlements in total.

In this regard, the principle of "Prosperous and safe neighborhood" introduced in the region and its implementation. For example, as of 2021, criteria for introducing a new system based on the principle of "Prosperous and safe neighborhood" in regional neighborhoods were developed and applied to all neighborhoods. In order to create convenience for residents in working with citizens' appeals, 1146 short-numbered "Sall-centre" centers have been launched, 2553 appeals have been received and resolved positively. The activities of 813 neighborhoods were studied and methodological and practical assistance was provided to them to eliminate the identified problems, and a model system was developed based on the specific aspects of the "Sarbozor" neighborhood in the Qamashi district and the "Varkanza" neighborhood in the Kitab district to reduce poverty. A new system was developed to solve the urgent issues and problems of the population in the neighborhood with a difficult socio-economic situation, on the example of the neighborhoods "Aqoltin" and "Shorbozor" in the Chirakchi district, "Bo'ston" in the Mirishkor district, and "Arabkhana" in the city of Karshi, and the problems in 77 neighborhoods were solved.

However, it is still known that the service buildings and material and technical conditions of some citizens' gatherings and neighborhood offices do not exist.

For example, as of 2021, they are 29 in Qamashi district, 22 in Karshi district, 22 in Koson district, 37 in Chirakchi district in 4 districts of Kashkadarya region. However, 1 thousand 163 neighborhood offices were built anew, 3 thousand 612 were reconstructed and repaired in the following years in order to strengthen the material and technical base of citizens' assemblies. "Neighborhood Center" complexes were established in 110 districts and cities, libraries were established in 4,319 neighborhood buildings.

Another important issue in the region is the employment of the population, especially the youth, and how much their employment affects the social indicators of

the neighborhoods. However, the employment indicators of young people are different in different regions of the republic, and in this regard, I. According to Bobojonov, in October 2018, a social survey was conducted by experts of the Republican Scientific Center for Population Employment and Labor Protection under the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations in order to determine the level of unemployment and poverty in the country. 330 citizens' self-government bodies, 3300 housewives and more than 17 thousand citizens participated in this survey. According to the results of the survey, the unemployment rate was the highest in Kashkadarya region, which was 9.7%. This indicator is the lowest in the city of Tashkent - 7.9%, and citizens who want to get a job made up 1,368.6 people. The unemployment rate among young people (under 30 years) is 15.1%, among 16-25-year-olds it is more than 17%, among women it is 12.9%.

Based on the above information, we explained the causes of the unemployment problem in the regional neighborhoods with the following factors. They are:

First of all, the majority of the residents of the regional neighborhoods live in rural areas, and there are enough problems to provide employment and attract the population to entrepreneurship in these areas;

Secondly, some neighborhoods are located far from the center, due to the disadvantage of their location and natural conditions;

Thirdly, the rate of population growth and migration processes are also important factors, and the fact that the birth rate is still high in the region also causes employment problems. For example, according to this indicator, Mubarak district takes the first place in our republic, and such rapid population growth is not only due to natural increase, but also due to population migration.

Fourthly, the fact that the majority of the unemployed segment of the population did not meet the demand for professions in high demand in the labor market also has an effect. This situation is visible in the neighborhoods of Tashkent.

As mentioned above, natural, economic and social factors play an important role in the formation and development of the region. Among the economic sectors, the basis

of the formation and development of regional neighborhoods is mainly agriculture and animal husbandry, partly handicrafts, and industry in the district center and urban neighborhoods. In this regard, neighborhoods are divided into three categories:

- neighborhoods where the majority of the population is engaged in agriculture and animal husbandry;

- neighborhoods where the majority of residents are engaged in agriculture;

- neighborhoods where the majority of the population is engaged in agriculture and crafts;

- neighborhoods where the majority of the population is engaged in productive entrepreneurship and industrial sectors;

- mixed neighborhoods. On the other hand, the neighborhoods specialized in agriculture are made up of neighborhoods engaged in horticulture, viticulture, and crafts. The status of production of the mahals specializing in agriculture and animal husbandry is also different. Relatively large neighborhoods were created in the districts where irrigated agriculture is developed, and the residential addresses of the population engaged in animal husbandry are not very large.

We found it necessary to divide Kashkadarya neighborhoods into the following categories according to their socio-demographic characteristics. It can be divided into the following groups according to the size of the neighborhoods:

- Small neighborhoods - population up to 500 people;
- Small neighborhoods - 500-1000 people;
- Medium neighborhoods – 1000-3000 people;
- Large neighborhoods - 3000-5000 people;
- Large neighborhoods - more than 5000 people.

Compared to many other regions of Uzbekistan, in Kashkadarya region, the role of small villages and hamlets located in mountain and sub-mountain areas is much more significant.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to partially optimize rural neighborhoods based on their classification in the conditions of Kashkadarya region. That is, in this area, it

is appropriate to combine neighborhoods with a population of up to 500 people into neighborhoods with a population of up to 100 people, 101-200 people, 201-300, 301-500 people. Such grouping reflects the economic, social and geographical characteristics of Kashkadarya region. It is not appropriate to use it in the conditions of other regions of our republic with high population density, where large villages make up the majority of villages. In general, there are large differences in the growth rates of the population of neighborhoods in the region at the district level. First of all, it is related to the lifestyle of the population, their employment, the influence of the environment, the level of urbanization and other factors.

It is noteworthy that in Kashkadarya and Surkhondarya regions, due to the unique natural conditions and location features of the region, a unique ethno-environment has been formed in family entrepreneurship and household farming. In particular, it is important to pay special attention to the development of these industries in the future, taking into account that a unique tradition has been formed in both regions as a result of the development of these industries. For example, if we take the example of the Surkhondarya region, in this regard, the carpet-making enterprise named "Astana Artisan" in the Termiz district, the small enterprise named "Turon" in the city of Termiz, the carpet weaving and felting workshop of the collective farm "Rabot" in the Boysun district, or "Shoyim" in the Sariosiyo district of the Surkhondarya region. " craft enterprise, wool processing has been started at the private enterprise "Dilafroz" in Sherabad, this enterprise produces 264 tons of high-quality wool yarn and supplies it to small textile enterprises.

In the example of Kashkadarya region, more than 600 artisans registered in the family business in Kitab district's "Oha Mashali" small enterprise, Chirakchi district's carpet weaving enterprise, Karshi city, Guzor, Kitab, Shahrisabz, Chirakchi, Qamashi and Muborak districts are working in the region. Workshops for making musical instruments, needlework, embroidery, goldsmithing and beadwork were established. This confirms that special attention has been paid to the types of traditional folk crafts in these regions.

However, there are also problems and shortcomings among the works carried out in the field in the regional neighborhoods. In particular, the share of imported goods has remained at a high level in the region with a large industrial potential. The needs of the domestic market for domestic products have not been studied. The possibilities of ready-made clothes and leather production enterprises have not been effectively used.

Until 2012, the domestic market of the region was poorly supplied with local products, which are in high demand in the region. There are no business entities producing plasterboard, various corrugated cardboard, disposable containers, paper bags, construction and agricultural machinery components, toothpaste and shampoo, nail products, even if their activity is not up to the demand level. In the field of services, 758 repairs, 1,078 veterinary services and meat shops, 1,214 bathroom and shoemaking (repair) services, 1,319 dry cleaning (dry cleaning) and household appliance repair services, 938 hairdressing and beauty salon services are needed among the population. business entities were not attracted to the fields despite the fact that

In general, since Kashkadarya region is a unique region of the southern region based on its geographical location, ethnodemographic status, geopolitical and geoeconomic factors, the cities and villages located in its territory, that is, neighborhoods, also differ from each other according to certain characteristics. That is, the region is a southern region that is distinguished by its geographical location, natural conditions, and ethnodemographic status.

At the same time, in terms of ensuring the employment of the population, especially the employment of young people, small businesses, private entrepreneurship areas, agricultural neighborhoods, horticulture and viticulture, and handicrafts are organized in the neighborhoods. confirmed that industries such as confectionery have

been formed and are developing. On the other hand, the state of production of the mahals specializing in agriculture and animal husbandry is almost similar to each other (in the mahals of Chirakchi, Dehqonabad, Kokdala, Yakkabog Districts). Relatively large and densely populated neighborhoods were created in districts where dryland and irrigated agriculture were developed, which showed that the residential areas of the population engaged in this type of occupation were formed in a unique way.

Current problems and suggestions for solving them:

First, according to research, 354 (43%) neighborhoods in Kashkadarya region do not have their own service buildings, 172 employees of neighborhoods work in enterprises, organizations, 138 in educational and healthcare institutions, 20 in the local administration building, and 24 in the neighboring neighborhood building. Similarly, 13 in Karshi, 27 in Guzor, 18 in Dehganabad, 31 in Qamashi, 26 in Karshi, 23 in Kasbi, 30 in Kitab, Kason

28, 4 in Mubarak, 12 in Nishon, 40 in Mirishkor, 96 in Chiroqchi, 57 in Shakhrisabz district, 40 in Shakhrisabz city, 62 in Yakkabog district do not have service buildings. It is necessary to build 205 out of 354 neighborhoods on the basis of public-private partnership, to transfer 75 buildings used by neighborhoods to the balance of the neighborhood, and to carry out construction works in the remaining 74 at the expense of additional sources of the local budget;

Secondly, in 84 out of 813 neighborhoods in the region, buildings are in need of capital or current repairs. Also, 230 pieces of furniture and 210 sets of computers in the citizens' gatherings have fallen into disrepair. Local hokims take into account the issue of allocating rooms for facilities that serve to meet the basic needs of the residents of the area (training courses, household service shops, beauty salons, etc.) it is necessary to take;

Thirdly, entrepreneurs living in rural areas, especially in remote and border areas, do not have enough opportunities to build their neighborhood buildings under the terms of public-private partnership. It is necessary to organize the activities of engineering companies within the framework of the system for the purpose of quality implementation of measures such as construction of neighborhood buildings, capital and current repairs, control of reconstruction works, development of technical assignments for project documents;

Fourth, only 579 (71 percent) of the neighborhoods in the region are connected to the Internet. The mechanism for the monthly payment of citizens' gatherings for using the Internet network has not been developed, and the financial source has not been indicated. Therefore, there are interruptions in the use of the Internet network of citizens' meetings at certain time intervals. For this reason, it is necessary to take measures to provide the Internet network to all citizens of the neighborhood and to solve the issue of monthly payment for use.

Fifthly, effective measures are not being taken to explain the meaning of the "Safe neighborhood" system and its implementation mechanisms to neighborhood activists and the public, and to use existing forces and tools to put it into practice. As a result, in 2021, total crime increased by 60.3 percent (3508/5813). In order to prevent violations in the neighborhoods, develop and effectively implement the criteria of the principles of "Safe House", "Safe Yard", "Safe Environment" in the neighborhoods in order to further develop the principle of "Prosperous and Safe Neighborhood"; - Implementation of the "Digital Neighborhood" complex information system for citizens' gatherings; development and implementation of model procedures, which provide effective and simplified mechanisms for discussion among the general public of violations that occurred in the territory of the neighborhood and the reasons and conditions for their commission; - based on advanced foreign experience, it is necessary to establish daily open information in the form of geoinformation of the analysis of the crime situation and criminogenic situation in the "Mahalla" single electronic database.

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